

**LITERATURE AND ART, DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE - A STRONG
FOUNDATION FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE SPIRITUAL WORLD
OF OUR PEOPLE**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6595318>

Nishonova Jumagul Ibrohimjon qizi

Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture, 2nd year master's degree in cultural studies

Abdullayeva Nasiba Ibrohimjon qizi

*Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture "Socio-cultural activities"
Third year student majoring in Education*

Annotation: *This article was written on August 3, 2017 at a meeting of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev with representatives of the creative intelligentsia of our country on topical issues related to the development of our national culture, literature and art.*

Key words: *Literature, creativity, cultural phenomenon, socio-cultural activity, art academy, music, art, folk art, baxshi, reading culture.*

On August 3, 2017, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev met with representatives of the creative intelligentsia of Uzbekistan on the topic "Development of literature and art, culture - a solid foundation for raising the spiritual world of our people." At the meeting, the President resolutely said, "We have great ancestors worthy of envy. We have unparalleled wealth that is worth envying. And I believe that if we are lucky, we will have a great future, a great literature and art, which we deserve." I can confidently say that it has already become the motto of the growing youth.

Addressing the artists, the President said: Today in this magnificent palace with you, dear people - prominent representatives of our national culture, famous poets and writers, well-known and young representatives of theater, cinema, music, art historians, journalists They said they were very happy to meet him. You, who consider the human heart, its worries and anxieties, the dreams and aspirations of the people, the feeling of love and devotion to the Motherland in unique words, tones and colors to be the meaning of your life. We all know that he is noble and honorable. I have known many of you for many years, I have read your works, I have always listened to and watched with great interest the songs, paintings, films and performances you have created. In short, I am happy to be a true fan of literature and art," he continued. I mean, we all know each other well, as one famous song puts it, "there's no stranger in the middle". That is why, if you agree, we will hold today's meeting in the spirit of such a sincere and open dialogue. it would be worthwhile to think carefully and come to a reasonable decision. In order to further develop our

spiritual life, a number of important documents have been adopted, including the decision to increase the culture of reading, improve the field of culture and art, the establishment of creative schools and centers named after our great artists in the regions. orders were also accepted. In this regard, the Alley of Writers is being built in Tashkent, where memorial complexes dedicated to the great figures of our literature are being erected, as well as the great enlightener Ibrat Domla in Namangan region, Hamid Olimjon, Zulfiya and Sharof Rashidov in Jizzakh, Khorezm region. It is with great pleasure that the memory of the late Hafiz Komiljon Otaniyazov, the Hero of Uzbekistan in Nukus, People's Poet Ibrayim Yusupov, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Aripov, Muhammad Yusuf in Fergana, Kashkadarya and Andijan regions was immortalized and schools and various monuments were erected. It is permissible to kidnap.

The Alley of Writers, which adds to the beauty of our capital, is a source of inspiration for the creative people. lightning is natural. Because it seems to me that the great representatives of our literature, who are watching us in this alley, wish us great success and give thanks to the Creator for the independence and freedom of our country. When it comes to the field of literature, there are thousands of talented young people living in different parts of the country, practicing poetry and storytelling, taking their first steps on the threshold of literature. It is not surprising that these young men and women, who today write introductory verses and rely only on the editors or master writers, will become the well-known writers and poets of tomorrow. In his pamphlet “Attention to Literature - Attention to Spirituality, Attention to the Future”, the first President I.A. Karimov said: It is no coincidence that one of the main goals is to educate great writers, great poets, great creators. Today, all the care and attention is focused on this goal.

From the first days of independence, youth policy has become one of the most important issues. For twenty-six years, this important issue has been on the agenda. On the contrary, year after year, the focus is on the youth. In this sense, the current conditions created for the education of young artists with a sharp taste and a high level of art can not be compared with any other period. As a result of such high attention, we are all well aware that in 2010 the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and the Ijod Public Foundation published the first books of a group of young artists and distributed them to all educational institutions free of charge. It is gratifying that many new talents are discovered every year as part of the My First Book project, which has become a good tradition. Many artists from our university have also been blessed with this happiness. As a logical continuation of the work in the field of literature, a number of measures are being taken to reveal the talents of young poets and writers, actors, artists and singers, journalists, to pay attention and care for them.

At the meeting, the President said: “We have no right to forget that attention to literature and art, culture is first of all attention to our people, attention to our future, as our great poet Cholpon said. But a natural question arises. What is the role and contribution of our creative intelligentsia in today's large-scale reforms, renewals and

changes in our country? ” they asked the creators. Of course, we always acknowledge with gratitude the great contribution of culture to the spiritual development of our people. We all know and appreciate that living in the path of high ideals, self-awareness, pride and self-sacrifice to protect our national interests is a virtue of the creative people. But let's put our hands on our chests and say honestly: will the current activity of our creative intellectuals satisfy our society, first of all, you, the people who are always burning and burning for the fate of the country? I think that today you feel the lack of activism in the field of culture and art, the spirit of living with new creative ideas and initiatives, the spirit of research. If we look at the current creative environment in our country, it seems that it is in a state of stagnation, and many of our artists are surrounded by their own worries and problems. However, shouldn't cultural and artistic figures always be at the forefront of society, inspiring people with their works, active civil position, towards noble goals and achievements?

As you know, from time immemorial, people have always had great respect and confidence in the creators. In Russian, it is no coincidence that they are highly regarded as "rulers of the mind." Because the Creator Himself has endowed you with such a unique talent and potential that not everyone has this quality. To be honest, I'm a little hesitant to talk about the power of literature and art in front of smart people like you. But do we use such a great, divine power wisely and effectively for the development of our country and people? Or, as our great writer Abdullah Qahhor put it, are we using the power of the atom to cut wood? Of course, among our artists there are many people who have a deep understanding of the spiritual and social duty of our people, the duty of childhood, who work tirelessly and are at the forefront of our society.

It is a great pleasure for me personally to see most of our selfless, active intellectuals in our time, creating in line with the times and setting an example for others. We can talk at length about their creative research and achievements, in particular, about the rich life of Uzbekistan today, for which we are grateful. However, it is no secret that such works are created mainly on the personal initiative of a poet or writer, artist or director, composer. The role and influence of our creative associations and government agencies, which need to be a real support and backbone in coordinating the creative process and supporting the arts in their birth, is not felt enough. Our creative organizations are lagging behind the requirements of the time in keeping pace with the rapidly changing times and effectively organizing their activities. In fact, shouldn't they work not only for today, but also for the future, and make well-thought-out, solid plans based on that? For example, how will the cultural development of Uzbekistan in 15-20 years, in the age of the Internet and high technology we live in today? Shouldn't the big and fair questions make us all think, first and foremost, the creative people who are the most advanced representatives of our people?

Analyses show that in today's activities of creative associations, the mood of entrepreneurship, mere showmanship, procrastination and indifference is becoming

more and more apparent. It is a pity that most of the leaders of creative organizations are accustomed to work only from above, and their activities do not show enthusiasm, initiative and organization for the common good. The President noted that in preparation for the meeting, he got acquainted with the Charters of our creative organizations, and the questions we ask today, the implementation of urgent tasks are in fact clearly defined in the Charters of these structures. So, it is safe to say that our creative organizations do not comply with the requirements of the Charter, the main document that forms the basis of their activities.

This is evidenced, for example, by the fact that organizations such as the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan and the Union of Composers do not pay attention to these requirements, in particular, do not hold congresses and elections on time. How can it be assessed that the Congress of the Composers' Union was held after 1995 - more than ten years later, and finally in 2014, at the request of higher organizations? However, today the main requirement for all governmental and non-governmental organizations is constant communication with the people, accountability to the people. Or if we take the activities of the Academy of Arts, which was once organized with high hopes, how can it be explained that there have been no elections here since 2003? With 10 full membership vacancies currently vacant at the academy, it is difficult to understand why no new elections are being held. This is, of course, the result of a lack of sense of responsibility, business acumen and creativity in these associations.

At the same time, the negative trends in the literary and artistic process, in particular, commercialization in the field of culture, the predominance of personal interests, the growing market for ideologically and artistically shallow works are of concern. Unfortunately, creative associations do not make a principled assessment of such cases, and do not make comprehensive practical proposals to eliminate them.

Why is there no critical spirit in our cultural life? Is it possible to be truly creative where there is no healthy criticism, debate and controversy? In this regard, the activities of the Arts Councils under the Ministry of Culture, Uzbekkino Agency, Composers' Union, Uzbekkonsert and other creative organizations are almost imperceptible.

Principled and qualified evaluation of works, films and performances, exhibitions and concerts, impartial and truthful reviews in the press, and the issuance of conclusions are becoming increasingly rare.

Another concern is that cooperation between creative associations is not well established. The creative relationship between the Academy of Arts, Composers, Writers, Journalists, Cinematographers' Unions and other organizations has almost come to a standstill, each frying in its own oil. However, in the activities of these structures there are many creative and social problems that need to be addressed together. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary to improve the existing legal and regulatory framework for the activities of literature and art, culture, mass media, strengthen the material and technical potential of the industry, materially and

spiritually stimulate the hard work of creative people. It should be noted that important and topical issues such as a radical overhaul and reform of the training system are left out of the attention of creative associations. Today, there are legitimate complaints among intellectuals about the proliferation of light books, shallow newspapers and magazines, and television and radio stations.

Currently, there are 1,513 media outlets of various forms of ownership in the country, as well as 122 publishing houses. But the question is whether all of them serve to develop our national idea, to raise the morale of our people. It is no secret that most of the private publishing houses were once organized with the wrong approach to have publishing houses in the provinces, and their material and technical base, human resources are extremely weak, which undermines the prestige of the book. . But practical suggestions on how to solve this problem on a legal basis are almost non-existent. I don't know about others, but in my opinion, the main reason for such a negative situation is the lack of regulation of the information market in our country. In this regard, quality and efficiency are important, not quantity. Well, the number of publishers should not be less than 122, but it should meet the demand. Today we pay special attention to the development of reading culture, the increase of scientific, artistic and political literature. But we must do all this carefully and do not allow the noble movement we have started to be discredited.

Unfortunately, the Uzbek Agency for the Press and Information, which is supposed to act as a competent and responsible body in the implementation of state policy in the field of press and information, is only an observer in this regard. That is why a new head of the Press and Information Agency was recently appointed. At the same time, a presidential decree is being prepared to radically reconsider the activities of this organization. Such creative work, I think, can be a source of inspiration for any artist and a theme for new works. If you do not write about such builders and engineers, field workers, passionate teachers and doctors, brave soldiers, young people, who are the real heroes of our time, who will create the artistic chronicle of the history of our country? If we do not mobilize our talents and skills for this sacred land, this noble people, Hazrat Navoi will say, what will we do to preserve this profession, where will we burn it?

It was also noted at the meeting that we have not been able to achieve any serious results in creating the image of a modern hero, an issue that has been pending for many years. Of course, there is no denying that there are some aspirations and efforts in this direction, as well as works of art and journalism, plays and films. But it is also true to say that many of them are heartless, coercive attempts, and that no mature and perfect works have yet been created that will take place in our cultural life. Frankly, it may seem a bit strange to some artists, who may think that it is impossible to create a good work, a complete image, by order. But I think that an artist - if he has a real talent - will be able to create a masterpiece on the basis of social order. In order to carry out this task, which is of great importance not only for our history, but also for our present and future lives, we need to find large sums of

money, if necessary, freely circulating foreign currency, to send our filmmakers abroad creatively. we are also ready to send on trips. Thank God, our current economic situation allows it.

There is another very important issue for us that will never be off the agenda, and I think it is necessary to dwell on it. And it is connected with the upbringing of our young generation, our children. As our great ancestor Abdullah Avloni said, this issue is really a matter of salvation, or destruction, happiness, or disaster for us, and it is a matter of issues that will never lose its relevance and importance, so to speak. In this sense, the "Take care of your own child!" The call is not only a dry slogan, but also a creative reconsideration of the responsibility of our creative organizations, so that every parent, every citizen can penetrate deep into the heart, into the practical action. rotating. We need to never forget one thing. It would be a mistake to say that the threat of "popular culture" comes only from abroad - from the West.

Unfortunately, this tragedy can happen to us and to ourselves. I'm not saying this from heaven. It is natural for any sane person to come to this conclusion after watching some newspapers and magazines, books, some music videos and movies, songs and dances. Worst of all, ignorance is on the rise in the field of art. When we say "ignorance", we usually mean religious ignorance, fanaticism. But today's life processes show that ignorance is common in all spheres, and if it is not fought in time, it can lead to very serious consequences. Today we face the scourge of ignorance in the economy, in education, in health care, in the cultural system, in all spheres of life, and this evil is in our hands and feet. Without getting rid of this shackle, there can be no talk of progress and development. As a child, I heard a story from my grandmother. The king of one country built a magnificent pool of white marble and ordered, "Every citizen should bring a cup of milk early in the morning and pour it into the pool." When one of the people who heard the decree said, "Who knows if I will take water instead of milk and pour it out instead of milk?" as long as they brought water by covenant. In vain I did not begin the introductory part of the essay with this narration. The example of the legend is that in my opinion, a person who feels one with the Motherland and has a clear conscience should have nothing but a desire to work for the development of the Motherland. Because the proverb "The sum of years is not life, the day that benefits the Motherland is life" is not in vain. The sages called his "second life" the glory of his service to the cause of the Motherland. The closer one feels to one's homeland, the more clearly and lovingly one imagines it as a living being. The Bible says, "Loving one's country is a matter of faith." Indeed, love for the Motherland begins with the heart and conscience of each person.

The concept of patriotism can be studied in two ways. The first is physically. That is, the place of birth. This feeling is inherent in all living things. From ants to elephants, he cares for the place where he was born and eats, and protects it when necessary. For example, let's try to break a beehive with a stick. The second concept - only the higher consciousness - is the spiritual state of man, or more precisely, the

spiritual state. It depends more on the heart, the mind, the emotions. Our compatriot, who lives abroad, witnessed an exemplary event: He was sitting with his German and Jewish friends in a famous restaurant. When the young man who was buying the newspaper approached, the Jew called him and bought a newspaper that would be published in Israel. "You don't know the language of example. Why did you buy the newspaper?" surprised the German. "Yes, unfortunately, I don't know my mother tongue, which is my shame. But this newspaper is published in my homeland. By buying it, I will be able to help my brothers there." In a way, this seemed to me to be a part of serving the Motherland. I know another man. I haven't seen any foreign-made clothes on her since I met her. He wears his own, albeit of poorer quality, and sees it as a small part of patriotism. At a time when our industry is on the rise, sometimes such particles are important.

In recent years, the field of spirituality has become a field of ideological struggle. When it became clear that overt and sometimes covert ideological attacks did not yield the expected results, geopolitical forces turned their attention to spirituality. The most serious danger in the spiritual realm is statelessness, the spread of the ideology of "world citizen". This is done by promoting the idea of cosmopolitanism.

Cosmopolitanism (Greek "cosmopolites" - citizen of the world) - a movement that weakens the love, loyalty and protection of the individual as a single homeland, his homeland, people and state. Harmful ideas such as statelessness, indifference to the present and future of the homeland, disrespect for its independence are based on cosmopolitanism and feed on it. A group of people who call themselves "citizens of the world" will be trained and will be taught that in the near future there will be no borders on Earth. Cosmopolitanism, which emerged as a reflection and denial of patriotism, has historically taken many forms. Where life is easy and the stomach is full, to keep the homeland, if the homeland is rich, to love it, to leave it when disaster strikes, to stay at home, to stare at other places - all this is statelessness. views.

It is not necessary to exaggerate the qualities of Uzbekistan. This people's spirit has made a great contribution to the enrichment of the history of the earth, to the rise of the spiritual world, and will continue to do so. But we must not only be proud of the past, but also act accordingly, remembering that we are responsible for the development of the Motherland, the future of the country and the continuation of the great tradition. Abu Nasr al-Farabi, an oriental encyclopedic scholar, described the state of equality in his City of Noble People as a state that aspired to virtue. The prudent policy of the head of our state to promote gender equality has not only revived our social and political activity in all spheres of society, but also ensured our direct participation in the process of reforms and changes. It is noteworthy that the policy of gender equality and the care provided not only applies to individual groups and organizations, but also to a wide range of women, who make up half of our population.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5953 of March 2, 2020, in order to create more opportunities for women to study in higher education, a separate 4% additional enrollment rate is allocated for them. can be said to have been another important step in the direction. According to the document, a system of admission of women to higher education institutions on the basis of additional state grants has been introduced. As a result, in 2020 alone, 940 women across the country were lucky enough to become students.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan F-4849 of February 14, 2017 “On the Strategy of actions on the five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021”
2. Sh.Mirziyoyev. The development of literature, art and culture is a solid foundation for the development of the spiritual world of our people, "People's Word", August 4, 2017.
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On holding the International Conference of Maqom Art" dated April 6, 2018.
4. www.fikr.uz
5. www.saviya.uz